

THE

4-DIMENSIONAL

QUANTUM GRAVITY

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METHODS

EINSTEIN'S GRAVITATIONAL CONSTANT

$$\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = 2,077 \times 10^{-43} \frac{1}{N}$$

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

$$\text{Velocity of light, } c = 299792458 \frac{m}{s}$$

$$\text{Newton's universal gravitational constant, } G = 6,67430 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg s^2}$$

$$\text{Dirac constant, } \hbar = 1,054571800 \times 10^{-34} Js$$

$$\text{Planck constant, } h = 6,62607015 \times 10^{-34} Js$$

$$\text{Boltzmann constant, } k_B = 1,380649 \times 10^{-23} \frac{m^2 kg}{s^2 K}$$

EXPANSION, ACCELERATION, REPULSION

$$\text{Hubble constant, } H_0 (s^{-1}) = 2,18 \times 10^{-18} s^{-1} (\text{Planck, 2018}), H_0 (s^{-1}) = 2,36 s^{-1} (\text{SHOES, 2021})$$

$$\text{Cosmological constant, } \Lambda = \kappa \rho_{DE} = \frac{3H_0^2 \Omega \Lambda}{c^2} = 1,08 \times 10^{-52} \frac{1}{m^2}$$

$$\text{Dark energy density, } \rho_{DE} = \frac{3H_0^2 \Omega \Lambda c^2}{8\pi G} = 5,217 \times 10^{-10} \frac{J}{m^3}$$

PLANCK UNITS

$$\text{Planck length, } l_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}} = 1,61625518 \times 10^{-35} m$$

$$\text{Planck mass, } m_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}} = 2,17643424 \times 10^{-8} kg$$

$$\text{Planck time, } t_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}} = 5,39124760 \times 10^{-44} s$$

$$\text{Planck area, } l_p^2 = \frac{\hbar G}{c^3} = 2,6121 \times 10^{-70} m^2$$

$$\text{Planck volume, } l_p^3 = \left(\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} = 4,2217 \times 10^{-105} m^3$$

$$\text{Planck energy, } E_p = m_p c^2 = \frac{\hbar}{t_p} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G}} = 1,9561 \times 10^9 J$$

$$\text{Planck force, } F_p = \frac{E_p}{l_p} = \frac{\hbar}{l_p t_p} = \frac{c^4}{G} = 1,2103 \times 10^{44} N$$

$$\text{Planck pressure, } P_p = \frac{c^7}{\hbar G^2} = \frac{E_p}{l_p^3} = 4,633 \times 10^{113} Pa$$

THE COSMOLOGICAL INFLATION

$$Ep = Pplp^3 = \frac{\hbar}{tp}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{Nhc\Lambda}{\lambda^2}$$

$$V_{mass} = \frac{Ep}{\rho_{DE}} = \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi Nlp\Lambda}$$

$$N = \frac{V_{mass}}{\frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3} = \sqrt{\frac{3\lambda^2}{8\pi^2 lp^4 \Lambda}}$$

$$A = \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi}$$

$$Rs = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi}$$

$$M = \frac{\lambda c^2}{8\pi G} \rightarrow mbit = \frac{M}{N} = \frac{\lambda lp^2 \Lambda}{6\kappa c^2} \rightarrow \lambda = \sqrt{\frac{6hc\kappa}{lp^2 \Lambda}}$$

$$Pq = \frac{mbit c^2}{\frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3}$$

$$E = Mc^2 = \frac{\lambda}{\kappa} = N Pq \frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3$$

$$V_{inflation} = \frac{Mc^2}{\rho_{DE}} = \frac{\lambda^3}{Nhc\kappa\Lambda}$$

$$\sum (mbit c^2) + \sum -(Pq \frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3) = 0$$

$$\sum (mbit c^2) + \sum -(G \frac{M mbit}{R}) = 0$$

THE BLACK HOLE THERMODYNAMICS

$$Nx = \frac{Mx}{mbit}$$

$$Rsch = \sqrt{N} lp^2 \frac{Nx}{N} = \frac{\sqrt{N} Nx lp^3 \Lambda}{6}$$

$$A = \frac{4\pi lp^2 Nx^2}{N} = \frac{4\pi lp^4 Nx^2 \Lambda}{6}$$

$$TH = \frac{N mbit c^2}{2\pi Nx kB} = \frac{N Pq \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3}{2\pi Nx kB} = \frac{6 \hbar c}{Nx lp^2 \lambda kB \Lambda}$$

$$S_{BH} = \frac{\pi lp^2 Nx^2 kB \Lambda}{6}$$

$$L = \frac{\sqrt{N} c mbit c^2}{80 x \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 Nx^2 \Lambda}$$

$$tev = \frac{80 x \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 Nx^3 \Lambda}{\sqrt{N} c}$$

THE FIELD EQUATIONS

$$EINSTEIN ' S FIELD EQUATION ; G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{Pp3tp}{\sqrt{N} N mbit c} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{Pp3tp}{Pq 2 N mbit c} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{Pp3tp\lambda}{N\sqrt{N}h} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{Pp3tp\lambda}{2 N Pq h} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{9 Pp}{\sqrt{N} Pq N 4\pi lp^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{4\pi\sqrt{N}lp^2}{Pq N \frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{Ep3tp\lambda}{h N \sqrt{N} lp^3} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{h}{Pq N \frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3 mbit c} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{3\hbar}{\sqrt{N} lp^3 N mbit c} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{3\hbar}{Pq 2 N lp^3 mbit c} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{3 H o^2 \Omega \Lambda}{c^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\lambda}{Pq N \frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{96\pi^2}{\lambda^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\lambda}{N mbit c^2} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{6}{Rs^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{4\pi\sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}}}{Pq N \frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{3\hbar c}{N\sqrt{N}lp^3 mbit c^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\sqrt{6\Lambda}lp^2\lambda}{3\hbar c} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{6}{N lp^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\lambda^2}{N h c} T_{\mu\nu}$$

NEWTON'S GRAVITATIONAL LAW

$$F = \left(G \frac{M_1 m_2}{r^2} \right)$$

$$N_1 = \frac{M_1}{m_{bit}}, N_2 = \frac{m_2}{m_{bit}};$$

$$F = \frac{N_1 N_2 \sqrt{N} l p^2 m_{bit} c^2}{N 2 r^2} = \frac{N_1 N_2 \sqrt{\frac{3}{2\Lambda}} m_{bit} c^2}{N r^2} = \frac{N_1 N_2 \lambda m_{bit} c^2}{N 2 \times 4 \pi r^2} = \frac{N_1 N_2 \hbar c}{N 2 \times 4 \pi r^2} = \frac{N_1 N_2 \hbar c}{N 4 r^2}$$

COSMOLOGICAL CONSTANT

$$\Lambda = \frac{3 H_0^2 \Omega \Lambda}{c^2} = \frac{6}{R_s^2} = \frac{6}{N l p^2} = \frac{P p 3 t p \lambda}{N \sqrt{N} \hbar} = \frac{3 \hbar c}{\sqrt{N} l p^3 n P q \frac{4}{3} \pi l p^3} = \frac{3 \hbar}{\sqrt{N} l p^3 N m_{bit} c}$$

NEWTON'S GRAVITATIONAL CONSTANT

$$G = \frac{\hbar c}{4 N m_{bit}^2} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{3}{2\Lambda}} c^2}{N m_{bit}} = \frac{\sqrt{N} l p c^4}{2 N \frac{4}{3} \pi l p^3 P q}$$

PLANCK CONSTANT

$$\hbar = m_{bit} c 2 \sqrt{N} l p^2 = m_{bit} c 2 \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}} = \frac{N m_{bit} c^2 4 m_{bit} c}{F_p} = \frac{N P q \frac{4}{3} \pi l p^3 4 m_{bit} c}{F_p} = \frac{8 \pi P q l p^4 \sqrt{N}}{3 c}$$

TIME DEPENDENT SCHRÖDINGER'S EQUATION

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \Psi(r, t) = \hat{H} \Psi(r, t)$$

POSITION SPACE WAVE FUNCTION

$$\Psi(r, t)$$

$$\Psi(r, t) = \Psi(r) T(t)$$

FUNCTION OF TIME, "THE PHASE FACTOR"

T

IN 3-DIMENSIONAL POSITION SPACE VECTOR (r) IS SPECIFYING POINT (x,y,z).

FUNCTION OF SPATIAL COORDINATES (Ψ)

$$x = r \sin \Theta \cos \Phi, \quad y = r \sin \Theta \sin \Phi, \quad z = r \cos \Theta$$

$$x = lp \sin \Theta \cos \Phi, \quad y = lp \sin \Theta \sin \Phi, \quad z = lp \cos \Theta$$

$$x = tp \sin \Theta \cos \Phi, \quad y = tp \sin \Theta \sin \Phi, \quad z = tp \cos \Theta$$

3D-SPATIAL POSITION SPACE COORDINATES CORRESPONDING TO
PLANCK SCALE SPATIAL INFORMATION: $\Psi(x, y, z)$

(Picture Wikipedia: Smite-Meister: Bloch sphere, 30 January 2009)

TIMESPACE QUANTUM

$$(r = lp = tp)$$

$$\hbar = \frac{8\pi Pq lp^4 \sqrt{N}}{3c}$$

MASS-MOMENTUM QUANTUM

$$\hbar = \frac{N \text{ mbit } c^2 4 \text{ mbit } c}{Fp} = \frac{N Pq \frac{4}{3} \pi l p^3 4 \text{ mbit } c}{Fp}$$

HOLOGRAPHIC PRINCIPLE

(Wikipedia: Smite-Meister: Bloch sphere, 30 January 2009)

Stereographic projection. Image: Jean-Christophe Benoist.

(Wikipedia: Stereographic projection: Image: Jean-Christophe Benoist)

(Wikipedia: Penrose diagram)

(Wikipedia : Minkowski space K. Aainsqatsi)

Wheeler-DeWitt-equation defines spacetime geometry.

$$\widehat{H}\Psi(\text{universe})=0$$

TIME IS EMERGENT DISTANCE BETWEEN EVENTS

HEISENBERG'S UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

QUANTUM OF ACTION

$$\hbar = mbit \ c \ 2 \sqrt{N \ lp^2} = mbit \ c \ 2 \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}} = \frac{N \ mbit \ c^2 \ 4 \ mbit \ c}{Fp} = \frac{N \ Pq \ \frac{4}{3} \ \pi \ lp^3 \ 4 \ mbit \ c}{Fp} = \frac{8 \ \pi \ Pq \ lp^4 \ \sqrt{N}}{3 \ c}$$

$$h = mbit \ c \ \lambda$$

QUANTUM UNCERTAINTY

$$\Delta x \approx 1 \ x \ 10^{-35} \ m \rightarrow \Delta x \approx 2 \ x \ 10^{-26} \ m$$

GRAVITATIONAL CERTAINTY

$$V \beta = \frac{lp^3}{N} = 1,9925 \ x \ 10^{-227} \ m^3$$

$$l \beta = \frac{lp}{\sqrt[3]{N}} = 2,711 \ x \ 10^{-76} \ m$$

$$t \beta = \frac{tp}{\sqrt[3]{N}} = 9,0409 \ x \ 10^{-85} \ s$$

$$GRAVITATIONAL \ ACTION : \hbar \beta = mbit \ c \ l \ \beta = mbit \ c^2 \ t \ \beta = 6,0955 \ x \ 10^{-137} \ Js$$

NO WAVE FUNCTION, JUST ACTION